

Effect of chemical herbicide on yield of dryland rice at Faizabad.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1976	1978
Control (no weeding)	0.6	0.6
Propanil (1.5 kg/ha)	1.7	1.8
Propanil (3.0 kg/ha)	2.1	2.2
MCPA (0.4 kg/ha)	1.6	1.6
MCPA (0.8 kg/ha)	1.8	2.0
2,4-D (0.5 kg/ha)	1.5	1.7
2,4-D (1.0 kg/ha)	2.0	2.1
Hand weeding (2 times)	2.3	3.0
C.D. (5%)	1.7	2.0

the N and all the P and K were applied at sowing; half the N was topdressed at tillering.

Major weed species 4 weeks after sowing were *Panicum colonum*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Paspalum* sp., *Phyllanthus niruri*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Ammannia baccifera*, and *Bonnaya* sp. Herbicides were sprayed by foot-operated Maruti sprayer 4-5 weeks after sowing. In 1977, the crop did not mature because of severe drought. In 1976 and 1978, yields were higher with chemical control but highest with hand weeding (see table). *h*

Yield losses to delayed weeding in direct-seeded, rainfed dryland rice

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Rainfed dryland rice in the hills of Uttar Pradesh is direct-seeded in winter fallow fields in March-April. Germination depends on soil moisture conserved from winter rains. Monsoon rains start in late June and the crop is harvested at the end of the rainy season, about 170 days to maturity. Hand weeding is the only weed control method.

To identify the critical time and number of weedings, nine treatments with three replications were tested in a randomized block design.

Grain yield without weed control was significantly lower than in the weed-free check (see table). Yield decreased with weeding delay, to a maximum loss when weeding was delayed to 100 days. Weeding at 40 days significantly reduced grain

Effect of hand weeding treatment on weed dry weight, control efficiency, grain yield, and straw yield in direct-seeded rainfed dryland rice, Almora, UP., India.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Weed dry weight (t/ha)	Weed control efficiency (%)
No weeding	0.2	0.6	2.9	—
One hand weeding 40 DE	1.4	2.4	1.4	53
One hand weeding 60 DE	0.9	1.7	1.7	42
One hand weeding 80 DE	0.6	1.7	1.8	38
One hand weeding 100 DE	0.3	0.8	2.2	26
Two hand weedings 40 and 60 DE	1.4	2.7	1.2	60
Three hand weedings 40, 60, and 80 DE	1.6	3.8	1.1	63
Four weedings 40, 60, 80, and 100 DE	2.2	4.1	0.7	76
Five hand weedings 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 DE	2.5	4.2	0.4	88
C.D. (5%)	0.50	2.00	0.66	

^aDE = days after emergence.

yield and additional weedings did not improve yields significantly until 4 weedings. Straw yield, weed dry weight, and

weed control efficiency showed similar trends. *h*

Soil and crop management

Effect of early drainage on yields

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To facilitate mechanical harvesting, paddy fields are drained early — at the ripening stage — but that causes an increase in imperfectly ripened grains and

a decrease in yield. If drainage is postponed, the paddy field could be too soft at harvest for the operation of a combine harvester. The effects of 5 different drainage times were measured at 5-day intervals from 10 days after heading to harvest. Preliminary results showed that the later the drainage, the greater the yield (see table). *h*

Effect of different drainage times on yield and yield components of mechanically harvested paddy in Taiwan.^a

Drainage time (DH) ^b	Yield (g/plant)	Panicle wt (g)	Spikelets per panicle (no.)	Fertility rate (%)	Wt of 1,000 grains (g)	Imperfectly ripened grains (%)
10	12.10 bc	1.71 d	111.2 a	76.4 b	20.8 c	43.8 a
15	11.98 bc	1.96 cd	108.0 a	77.0 b	24.1 b	24.4 b
20	13.93 b	2.22 bc	105.4 a	83.7 ab	25.4 b	19.8 b
25	16.68 a	2.63 ab	116.8 a	84.0 ab	27.5 a	14.8 b
30	18.75 a	2.83 a	117.7 a	91.8 a	27.0 a	13.3 b

^aAny 2 means with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bDH = days after heading.

Transplanting made easy — broadcasting of seedlings

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Transplanting costs equal about 15% of total rice production cost. Transplantings delayed by labor shortages result in lowered yield caused by low temperature limitation in subtropical India. A low-cost, low-labor transplanting method must be developed.